

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN THE ONLINE PRODUCT
RECOMMENDATION AND CUSTOMER SUPPORT SYSTEM: THE
MEDIATING ROLE OF TWO-WAY SYMMETRIC COMMUNICATION

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Abstract

Artificial Intelligence in different aspects is among the mainstream phenomenon today. Especially the role of Artificial Intelligence in upgrading and improving the online retail sector by facilitating balanced communication is of greater significance. This research also examines the role of Artificial Intelligence in product recommendation and customer support systems. The researchers gathered a sample of n= 310 customers of the online retail sector in Pakistan. Theoretically supported by the Two-Communication communication model, this study's conceptual model is supported by the Structural Equation Modelling (SEM). Results revealed that transparency and consistency significantly affect Artificial Intelligence, indicating both features are common in AI technology today. Further, the effect of Artificial Intelligence in the product recommendation system also remained significant. Finally, the mediating effect of Two-way Communication on the product recommendation system also remained significant, affirming the role of balanced communication in providing customers with improved online retail services. The study concluded that AI in online retail had yielded several fruitful results. On the other hand, two-communication further increases the value of online retail products and services. Consequently, these customers increase their attention and satisfaction, which is possible only when they are equally heard and provided with the best they want.

INTRODUCTION

Communication is a crucial factor of organizations especially for the growth and development of the retail sector (Szwajca, 2017). According to Grewal et al (Grewal et al., 2020), an excellent communication capability can positively influence the customers in many ways. By keeping in view, the importance of communication, retail sector organizations enjoy several benefits after enhancing their communication strategies. Riegger et al (Riegger et al., 2021) cited an example of customer satisfaction due to communication. As customers mostly feel confident

when they are provided with equal communication opportunities, they are more likely to share their opinion about their positive experiences. On the contrary, Shankar et al (Shankar et al., 2021) consider bad experiences as sometimes customers' turnover, harming the growth and sales goals without lodging their complaints. Another factor regarding importance of communication in the retail sector is the "trust building". (Bonetti et al., 2018). According to Chen et al (Chen et al., 2022), and their colleagues, even simple things such as welcoming them when they

enter in a store (physically or virtually) can strengthen their bond with the retail organization. In this regard, when communication is even more feasible due to digital channels, retailers worldwide are more actively communicating and meeting the customers' standards. According to Savastano (Savastano, 2019), considering the importance of communication, adopting new technology and design relevant strategies is one of the top priorities for the retailers. As noted by Riar et al (Riar et al., 2021) customers can be attracted and convinced by different factors. However, among these factors, effective communication through instant availability all the efforts may get in vain. As customers prefer online communication, the retail sector organizations having technology for customer interaction and support, enjoy more customer satisfaction, improved services, and increased sales and growth.

Similarly, Varian (Varian, 2018) consider only effective online communication as providing potential support and guidance to the customers which they search. However, today, when online communication is booming and communication feasibility is inevitable, Dwivedi et al (Dwivedi et al., 2021) argued that retail organizations are readily integrating advanced technology, i.e., Artificial Intelligence to provide the customers with maximum and unhindered support. As noted by Davenport & Ronanki (Davenport & Ronanki, 2018) Artificial Intelligence is radically redefining the landscape of customer support system. From visual search to the automated messages, AI customer support Chatbots are helping companies to better support their customers at touch points in their online buying journey. These Chatbots provide with the improved, two-way communication feasibility as they use the existing resources i.e., (Cockburn et al., 2018). Consequently, a better customer system further results in increased customer loyalty and satisfaction, leading to more technology-reliance and less consideration towards the conventional approaches for the customer support system (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2019).

1.1 AI Technology in Pakistani Online Retail Sector:

Pakistan has a strong e-commerce market. Retailers in online Pakistani market place pay a special

consideration to cater the customers' needs in a best possible manner (Belouaar et al., 2022). According to Baba and their colleagues, today when AI technology has widely replaced the human workplace, the Pakistani online retailers are also enjoying its full benefits. Notably, the recent data shows a strong revenue generation in Pakistani e-commerce sector that is predicted to increase 15.86% from 2023 to 2025. Notably, Pakistani is ranked 118th out of 172 countries in the Artificial Intelligence Readiness Index (AIRI). A report published by Oxford Insights indicates the willingness of both public and corporate sector organizations in Pakistan to incorporate AI to upgrade their existing operating patterns (D'souza et al., 2021).

In the past several years, AI has become a top priority for enterprises across industry sectors and even government bodies. (Kuteynikov et al., 2022). According to Sujatha and Karthikeyan (Sujatha & Karthikeyan, 2021), during the past few years AI has become a top priority for the retail sector organizations in Pakistan. A survey conducted by Baba and their colleagues (Baba et al., 2022), indicted that 86% of business owners and stakeholders consider AI as a part of their strategic priority. These individuals also consider AI technology as ensuring the business goals' acquisition increased reputation, greater accessibility to prospective customers, and increased sales and growth in the future. The increasing role of Artificial Intelligence in product recommendation and customer support systems in Pakistan needs be examined through the factors that impact its future progression in retail sector.

1.2 Study Objectives and Structure:

The importance of Artificial Intelligence in the online retail sector is highlighted above. This study also acknowledges this importance and aims to examine the role of Artificial Intelligence, accompanied by transparency and consistency, in production recommendation and direct customer support systems. The article is arranged as the first section involves an introduction and statement of the problem. The second section involves literature supporting the study problem, further supporting the formation of study hypotheses and conceptual framework. The third section highlights the methods and approaches used in this research, while the fourth section is based on

the data analysis and results. The fifth section discusses the results, and finally, the sixth section involves the conclusion, study limitations, and recommendations.

2. Review of Literature:

2.1 Transparency in AI-Enabled Customer Support:

According to Diwanji et al (Diwanji et al., 2022), Artificial Intelligence has transformed the landscape of communication in the consumer culture. Particularly, These Chatbots are specially designed to have human-like interaction with the users by sending and receiving messages for automating a business process. (Kushwaha et al., 2021).

According to Beerbaum (Beerbaum, 2022), sometimes critics also question the credibility of information during a Chatbot and human communication process. The recent examples of different online retail stores are illuminating to answer this criticism as product information, observability, and comparison with other related products are explicit (Nolan, 2023). Notably, these Chatbots use Artificial Intelligence (Machine Learning Algorithms) to initiate interaction through text conversation and voice commands. This technology comprises near to zero marginal cost, that comes up with several benefits to the customers, as they are based on transparency and credibility of information (Li & Lu, 2021).

H1: Transparency has a positive effect on Artificial Intelligence

2.2 Consistency in AI-Enabled Customer Support:

According to Yang & Hu (Yang & Hu, 2022), consistency is a simplest yet most significant way to create a potential customer support service. As consistency is the key to create and gratify the customer needs in a best possible way. Further validated by Qiu et al (Qiu et al., 2022), as their study revealed thwart more than 40% of the customers indicated consistency as one of the most prominent reasons behind the repurchase from the same retailer. Adam et al (Adam et al., 2021) argued that, consistency is considered as one of the fundamental of online retail services, along with prompt and effective suggestions and recommendation.

Similarly, integrating Artificial Intelligence creates consistency in the customer support services (Cui et

al., 2021). Here Kautish & Khare (Kautish & Khare, 2022) cited a comparison of conventional online customer support system and Artificial Intelligence enabled system. As stated, the customers do not prefer services that contain long queries, waiting systems and a human representative who may not be available when the help or recommendation is required. All these emphasize and highlight the importance of consistency, where technology is aligned and available to meet the customer demands (Esch et al., 2021). According to Davenport & Ronanki (2018), if the customer support is inconsistent, he bad customer experiences may take place as the customers not necessarily share their opinion with the retailer, they will necessarily their experiences with the peers, leading to increased inconsistency and negative reputation.

H2: Consistency has a positive effect on Artificial Intelligence

2.3 Artificial Intelligence for Production Recommendation Purposes:

According to Fedorko et al (Fedorko et al., 2022), online retail stores contain a verity of products and services for the customers. Here, Nagy & Hajdú (Nagy & Hajdú, 2020) cited an example of one of the leading Ecommerce platform “Amazon” that contains an extensive AI-based product recommendation system to its customers. As if a customer has purchased an online leather jacket, the next time they may open the Amazon, its algorithms will suggest more leather products, including those especially required during the winter season.

Alkhayyat & Ahmed (2022) argue that an Ecommerce not only provide their customers with valued products but also aim to provide their customers with eventful and improved shopping experiences. According to Grover et al (2022), now the customers do not need to visits shopping malls and spend their time in making decisions, rather, a remote device connects us with world’s leading retail stores.

H3: Artificial Intelligence has a positive effect on Production Recommendation system.

2.4 Artificial Intelligence for Direct Customer System:

Precisely speaking, there are two types of Artificial Intelligence including Narrow AI and General AI.

Examples of Narrow AI include voice and speech recognition system like personal assistants, Medial AI examining MRI results, and self-driving vehicles. The general AI is mostly seen in movies, mostly the robots and system that learn and act on their own (Linden et al., 2003). In this regard, Narrow AI is mainly used for the customer support systems. The systems containing Narrow AI provide the customers with the answers to their questions, respond to their requests, and are based on problem-solving behaviors. According to Babic et al (Babic et al., 2021), the Narrow AI in customer support include Machine Learning to assess and comprehend the customer data, chatbots that answer customers’ queries, Natural Language Processing (NLP) for voice recognition, customer self-service, and others (Perez-Vega et al., 2021).

It is notable that, AI in customer system is not a new phenomenon. The very first chatbot named “ELIZA” was developed during 1960s. However, for the customer support system, the first chatbot was developed during 1990s, introducing new approaches regarding text communication (Nam et al., 2021). According to Ameen et al, new trends and AI incorporation in the customer support system also benefitted the brands and organizations.

H4: Artificial Intelligence has a positive effect on the direct customer Support.

2.5 Two-Way Communication in Product Recommendation System:

Communication is the key to gain customer satisfaction and loyalty (Hesamamiri & Bourouni, 2016). When customers are equally heard, their opinion is given importance, and they are provided with best options (Nguyen, 2019), they are more likely to stay consistent with selecting the retail stores and their services (T. Cheng, 2019). In this regard, Low et al (Low et al., 2021) consider Artificial Intelligence as a great tool that provides the customer support system with strong customer service. Besides, they also help the customers to find the suitable products, even if they are unable to find the products they want, the similar products from the different brand are also recommended by the AI chatbots (Stöckli & Khobzi, 2021).

According to Sharma et al (Sharma et al., 2021), Artificial Intelligence is not merely recommending the support, but also listening to the customers, collecting their feedback, acknowledge their online presence whenever they want, that also attract the other customers. As noted by Mumuni et al (Mumuni et al., 2020), a good communication helps the retail sector to develop trust with their customers and articulate their expectations, challenges and their needs. Notably, two-way communication improves the client relationships and add even more leads to the retail organization (Helberger et al., 2018).

H5: Two-way Communication has a significant indirect effect Direct customer Support

Figure 1: Conceptual Model of Current Research

Research Methodology:

According to (Cousin, 2005), case study designs are based on objective approach to maximize the precision and conclusions can be drawn through the

hypothesized assumptions. By keeping in view, the nature of study problem and objectives, the researchers used case study design for this research. Besides, the data gathering was done by using close-

ended survey questionnaires, that were self-proposed by the researcher and later, tested for the validity and reliability (Fincham, 2008). Data gathering was done from July 15th 2022 to September 6th 2022. Finally, the gathered data was manipulated and coded to perform the Structural Equation Modelling (SEM).

3.1 Sampling Approach:

The population of current research involves customer of online retail sector in Pakistan. However, to narrow down the study sample, the researchers selected n= 2 cities (Lahore and Rawalpindi). Further, the researchers selected a sample of n=310 online customers have an experience of online shopping. The data was gathered by randomly selecting the individuals as they were contacted through emails and their consent to participate was taken. The random selection was based on simple random sampling approach, in which all the units in the population had an equal chance of selection. After the data collection, the researchers carefully checked the questionnaires and found the response rate at 99.0% as, n= 3 questionnaires were missing or not returned by the respondents.

3.2 Common Method Bias:

According to Çizel et al (Çizel et al., 2020), Common Method Bias is common in the studies where data all the variables are gathered by the same person in the same measurement context by utilizing the same item in context and characteristics. Notably, the bias appears when the proposed relationship between the study variables is inflated (Myers et al., 2010). Thus, examining the Common Method Bias (CMB) in this research remained at 41%, that is less than 50% as suggested by MacKenzie & Podsakoff (2012).

Analysis and Results:

As the study involves Structural Equation Modelling (SEM), the researcher adopted two criteria to examine the study model in details (Ali et al., 2021). First, the internal consistency or correlation among the study construct is examined by using the Convergent Validity assessment. For the relevant purpose the researcher calculated the Factor Loading and Average Variance Extracted values. As summarized in the Table 1, the majority of the Factor Loading has satisfactory values. Besides, the Average Variance Extracted values also remained satisfactory indicating them as exceeding 0.5 (Habes et al., 2022). Overall, the results of Convergent Validity analysis revealed that the items are internal consistent with each other.

Table 1: Summary of Internal Consistency Assessment

Latent Variables	Survey Items	Loadings	Average Variance Extracted
Transparency	TRN1	.813	.802
	TRN2	.743	
	TRN3	.838	
	TRN4	.755	
Consistency	CON1	.723	.850
	CON2	.892	
	CON3	.842	
	CON4	.808	
Artificial Intelligence	AI1	.813	.804
	AI2	.796	
	AI3	.415	
	AI4	.571	
Two-way Communication	COM1	.883	.934
	COM2	.928	
	COM3	.991	
	COM4	-.083	
Product Recommendation	REC1	.814	.868
	REC2	.911	
	REC3	.789	
	REC4	.881	
Direct Customer Support	DCS1	.871	.884
	DCS2	.899	
	DCS3	.901	
	DCS4	.866	

The construct reliability of the measurement model was analyzed (See Table 2) by calculating the Cronbach Alpha and Composite Reliability values (Allen, 2017). First, the values obtained by using Cronbach Alpha revealed a satisfactory performance

as exceeding (.790-.903) the threshold value 07. Also, assessing the Composite Reliability also remained satisfactory (.700- .821). The relevant analysis revealed that the measurement model well contains the Construct Reliability (Cheung & Wang, 2017).

Table 2: Summary of Construct Reliability Analysis

Latent Variables	Cronbach Alpha	Composite Reliability
Transparency	.863	.750
Consistency	.811	.734
Artificial Intelligence	.800	.821
To-Way Communication	.790	.819
Product Recommendation	.841	.700
Direct Customer Support	.903	.794

After the survey items evaluation, , the researcher found the square of Average Variance Extracted values as satisfactory and filling the discriminant validity criteria (Shiu et al., 2011). Besides, the correlations regarding Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio were also acceptable (.291) (Voorhees, 2016),

indicating that the discriminant validity of the measurement model is also established (See Table 3 and 4). Thus, it is affirmed that all the correlations, squares of AVE values, and HTMT values are satisfactory fulfilling the discriminant validity criteria.

Table 3: Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio Scale

	TRN	CON	AI	COM	REC	DCS
TRN						
CON	.323					
AI	.049	.039				
COM	.426	.322	-.004			
REC	.788	.347	.035	.491		
DCS	.795	.504	-.183	.485	.886	

Table 4: Fornel Larcker Criterion

	TRN	CON	AI	COM	REC	DCS
TRN	.643					
CON	.281	.722				
AI	.035	.133	.646			
COM	.319	.046	.012	.872		
REC	.602	.255	.009	.323	.753	
DCS	.695	.265	.067	.371	.061	.781

Table 5: Model Fit Analysis by the Amos

Criterion	Estimated Model	Saturated Model
SRMR	.082	.082
NFI	.609	1.257
Chi-square	1062.145	1062.145
d_ULS	.610	1.277
d_G	.516	.516
Rms Theta	.071	

The researcher examined the Goodness of Fit to assess the extent to which observed data fit into the expected data. The Goodness of Fit provided with NFI, RMSEA, d_G, Chi-square and U_ULS values. According to Chwialkowski et al (2018), the variations between obtained correlations and model highlighted correlations smaller than .85 are considered as good measures for the model. In this

research, the RMSEA value remained at 0.82. Besides, if the NFI values are greater than .90, they also indicate the Goodness of Fit. According to Sun (Sun, 2005), NFI is the ratio of the chi-square value of the proposed model as also shown this model. The NFI value remained at 1.57, indicating that the research parameters are large. Hence, it is affirmed that the Goodness of Fit for the proposed model was sufficient.

Table 6: Coefficients of Determination R²

Constructs	R ²
Transparency	.365
Consistency	.673
Two-way Communication	.312
Production Recommendation	.511
Direct Customer System	.602

According to Piepho (Piepho, 2019), Coefficients of Determination examines the extent to which variability is found into endogenous variables due to exogenous variable(s). This correlation is found from 1 to 0, indicating a “perfect fit”. Correlation of Determination in this research from strong to moderate level variability among the endogenous

variables (Filho et al., 2011). Precisely speaking, the results revealed, 67.3% variation in the Consistency, 31.2% in the Two-way Communication, 36.5% in the Transparency, 51.1% in the Product Recommendation, and 60.2% variation in the Direct Customer Support (See Table 7).

Table 7: Path Analysis, Regression Weights

Relationship	β	t	P
Transparency → Artificial Intelligence	.303	-.094	.025*
Consistency → Artificial Intelligence	.124	2.370	.018**
Artificial Intelligence → Production Recommendation	.208	.097	.063*
Artificial Intelligence → Direct Customer Support	.103	1.175	.240
Relationship	β	Indirect Effects	P
Artificial Intelligence → Two-way Communication → Direct Customer Support	.212	5.960	***

According to Soltanzadeh (2015), Path Analysis is a formal approach to determine the cause-and-effect relationships between the study variables. The relevant is also known as Analysis of Covariance Structure, Covariance Structure Analysis, and Structural Equation Modelling (SEM), It is also applied for analyzing the language system, memory system, motor attention, and visual system (Nakagawa et al., 2018). However, in the current research is used for the conventional patterns’ mainly confirmatory than exploratory. Consequently, the current research used SEM as model drive rather than the data driven, indicating it as more causal than correlated. Thus,

results revealed that, most of the causal relationship proposed in this study, remained validated. First, the researchers examined the effect of Transparency on the Artificial Intelligence in the Product Recommendation and Direct Customer Support. As noted by (Perez-Vega et al, 2021) transparency is a highly considerable phenomena for online retail stores. The more transparent approaches are implied, the more customers will be attracted, leading to an increased customer satisfaction and loyalty. In this regard, the proposition remained significant (p> .025), indicating that transparency is widely being followed and practiced by AI-enabled retail stores in Lahore

and Rawalpindi by their customer support and recommendation services. In the H2 of this research, the researcher examined the effect of Consistency on Artificial Intelligence as also witnessed by Bawack et al (2021) in their study. Results revealed a potentially significant effect of Consistency on Artificial Intelligence ($p > .018$). As noted by (Yang & Hu, 2022), a customer support system accompanied by consistency is considered as reliable. Providing the customer with consistent recommendations, answer to their questions, and adopting a consistent approach in solving their problem adds more value to the store reputation.

Further, the H3 and H4 of this study proposed a significant effect of Artificial Intelligence on the Product Recommendation and Direct Customer Support System. According to Esch et al (2021), Artificial Intelligence in the product recommendation and customer support is the need of the day. Companies that understand and acknowledge the importance of automation, improved human-computer interaction, and higher customer satisfaction are more likely to adopt Artificial Intelligence to upgrade the support and product recommendation system. Findings revealed that, Artificial Intelligence in the Lahore and Rawalpindi retail sectors has a significant effect on the Production Recommendation system ($p > .063$). However, the effect of AI on Direct Support remained insignificant ($p > .240$). According to Beerbaum (2022), as a prominent part of Machine Learning approach, AI for the product recommendation is based on algorithms that help to predict and users' choices and provide with the most relevant suggestions in online retail stores. Finally, the researcher proposed an indirect (mediating) effect of Two-way Communication on the Product Recommendation system. As noted by Stöckli & Khobzi (2021), two-way communication involves a direct interaction, where all the involved parties. The exchange of information is based on back and forth, that affirm that the information is received and feedback is provided accordingly. This two-way communication facilitates the customers as they directly or indirectly provide the customers with opportunity to speak up and inform about their requirements, that are fulfilled in a best possible manner (T. Cheng, 2019). Findings revealed that the mediation of Two-way Communication remained

significant on the Direct Customer Support ($p > .000$), indicating the contributive role of Two-way Communication in strengthen the Product Recommendation system though the Artificial Intelligence.

3. Discussion on Results:

Two-way communication is one of the extensive and ethical models in communication, marketing, advertising, and Public Relations. Talking about its applicability in the current research, the relevant model provided with strong theoretical background (Razumnikov, 2022). As noted by Oncioiu et al (2021), Two-way communication is takes place where both the sender and recipients switch to each other's position during interaction. Relevant to this study, two-way communication takes place when a retail store sends a message, customers' share their response, and then the store provides the customer with best options and also support in decision-making process. For this purpose, today brands are more conscious about improving their services, and switching to 24/7 availability for their customers (G. J. McLean, 2017). Consequently, incorporating Artificial Intelligence is considered a strategic decision, that not only provides the customers with relevant recommendations and support them but also, helps the retail organization to meet their desired goals (G. McLean & Wilson, 2016).

This research also remained consistent with the idea of integrating AI in product recommendation and customer support for better services (Jabeen et al., 2022).. The study respondents indicated their wider agreement with the importance, benefits, and positive outcomes attributed to Artificial Intelligence in their online systems (Tussyadiah, 2020). First, the study hypothesises "**Transparency has a positive effect on Artificial Intelligence**". This hypothesis was consistent with the idea proposed by Li & Lu (2021), indicating Artificial Intelligence as learning and practicing transparency as a core consideration. According to the respondents, the product recommendation system stays updated about the product features, availability, and suitability. As soon as a query appears, the system instantly responds and provide the customers with the best possible answers to their questions. The second hypothesis "**Consistency has a positive effect on the Artificial Intelligence**" also indicated with the idea

proposing Consistency as an important element of Artificial Intelligence especially the Machine Learning approaches. The respondents indicated their stronger agreement with the fact that, the system developers and administrators keep a regular check on the system, monitor its activities, and update so that the consistency may be ensured. Precisely speaking, the

respondents revealed that consistency is an important element of the AI-enabled system (Stöckli & Khobzi, 2021). The ideas and recommendations that are consistent with the clients search history, needs, and keywords (text) are provided to keep consistency under consideration.

Furthermore, the third study hypothesis “**Artificial Intelligence has a positive effect on Production Recommendation system**” indicated the importance of AI technology in efficiently regulating the product recommendation system for the customers. As noted by Beerbaum (2022), AI ensures recommendation engine is making instant and to the point recommendation for every customer that may meet their preferences and needs. The study respondents also remained agreed as indicated that with the Artificial Intelligence, the product recommendation system is getting better. The system is strongly focused at making recommendations based on the customers’ preferences rather than the product specifications (Nguyen, 2019). The respondents also showed agreement with the statement that an instant recommendation system also helps them to search and buy the products easily. These products are relevant, and suitable to their price range, hat also saves their time and efforts (Sharma et al., 2021). The study hypothesis “**Artificial Intelligence has a positive effect on the direct customer Support**” was aimed at the role of Artificial Intelligence providing support to the customer and facilitate them and answer their questions. The study respondents answered that, Artificial Intelligence has added efficacy in the customer support system. Today, when the human force is replaced by the Artificial Intelligence, providing the customer support is one of the core considerations for these technological systems (Alkhayat & Ahmed, 2022). Notably, the respondents considered Artificial Intelligence as the

extension of the direct customer support services (Perez-Vega et al., 2021). Here they disagreed with the statement assuming Artificial Intelligence as replacing the human force in monitoring and customer support systems.

Finally, the last hypotheses “**Two-way Communication has a significant indirect effect Direct Customer Support**” shows the importance of balanced communication in product recommendation system. According to Yu et al (Yu et al., 2021), the direct customer support system usually works according to the customer demands and needs. The customers share the details about the products they need, ask the question about a product, or even file their complainants. All these concerns are addressed and answered here customers’ feedback is given much importance to alter or change the products as per the suggestion and complaints. Thus, the respondents also agreed that, tow-way communication not only helps them to gratify their needs but also, it fulfils their share their opinion confidentially and feel valued by the retailer (Y. Cheng & Jiang, 2022). As noted by Tosyali (Tosyali, 2021), Artificial Intelligence in customer support stands for Chatbots, Machine Learning, Ntaural, Language Processing, and many others. There is increased usage also shows its relevance with the Lahore and Rawalpindi’s sustainable development, that further increases its interest in the retail sector as besides the economic goals, providing the customers with the best is among the primary goals of the retail sector organizations.

Conclusion:

An improved customer support and product recommendation system is a crucial factor of success in the retail sector. Results of this study remain consistency with this idea as the respondents also agreed on the customer support and product recommendation systems as widely facilitating them in multiple ways. However, these both systems were accompanied by Artificial Intelligence, indicating better performance and improved services through technology integration. Other factors such as consistency and transparency also accelerate upgrading the services, as also witnessed by the current research. Thus, it is concluded that today, Artificial Intelligence is equipped by transparency and consistency to improve the services in the online retail stores. The results of AI in online retail stores are increased customer satisfaction, brand trust, loyalty, and further strong reputation. Notably, two-way communication is another important factor that adds more value to the retail services and products as, winning the customers' attention and loyalty is only possible when they are equally heard and provided with the best they want.

6.1 Limitations:

This study comes up with some primary limitations. First, the researcher only selected the retail stores in the Lahore and Rawalpindi as the sample, while the other different organizations in other cities of Pakistan are also using AI for customer support and product recommendation. Second, the researchers only on the AI, whereas many companies are practicing customer support and product recommendation with human force. Finally, the third limitation involves using only to tactics of communication and customer support system (transparency and consistency), however there are five other different tactics that can be further used by future researchers to examine an overall integration and effect of these tactics on customer's attitude towards a brand or online retail store.

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